

ISic3480

Sikel inscription on wall of a tomb

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Palagonia

Provenance

Tomb 15 was identified in 1990 at the Coste di S. Febronia, near Palagonia

Coordinates

37.32519, 14.76745

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palagonia, in situ

Physical Description

A rock-cut tomb (Tomb 15) in the Coste di S. Frebonia, consisting of an entry and single chamber, with inscriptions on two walls, of which this is the left-hand wall

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

The text is engraved on the left-hand wall as one enters the tomb, in a single line, from right to left, with two further large letters separated from the main text

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters of the archaic Greek alphabet: sigma rendered with a single wavy line; of the two alphas, one is regular, the other the arrow-head form 'alpha siculum'. Of the main group, qoppa is the tallest at 130 mm; of the two alphas, the regular is 170 mm, the sikel form 110 mm

Letter heights:

Line 1: up to 130 mm

Line 2: 110-170 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. ΤΟΨΙ

2. ΑΑ

Apparatus

Text based on editions of Cordano

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645101

EDCS 70901063

PHI 336139

PHI 337256

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0931.2

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1300.2

Cordano, F. 1999. Iscrizioni dal territorio di Palagonia e Mineo (Catania). *XI Congresso Internazionale di Epigrafia Greca e Latina (Roma, 18-24 settembre 1997). Atti.* Rome. pp. 679-685. At 679-681 no.2 dr

Cordano, F. 1997-1998. Iscrizioni dal territorio di Palagonia e Mineo (Catania). *Kokalos*. 43-44: 165-171. At 165-169 no.2

Cordano, F. 2012. Iscrizioni monumentali dei Siculi. *Aristonothos*. 4: 165-184. At 165 no.1

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